

Interactive guide for selecting methods for ecosystem service quantification and mapping

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This guide is part of ***Nature as an Ally: Ecosystem Services Manual for Planners***, and it aims to facilitate the rapid identification of appropriate methodologies for the quantification and mapping of ecosystem services, according to specific objectives and user profiles.

To do so, we propose a series of dichotomous (YES or NO) questions, according to your relative alignment with each decision point. This way, you can proceed to new questions and possible recommendations. You will also find options to return to the previous question or go back to the beginning by clicking the corresponding option.

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1

Why are you trying to apply the ecosystem services approach?

To conserve biodiversity in my system or area of interest, regardless of that biodiversity's contribution to human well-being. My central interest is biological conservation for the intrinsic value of species, regardless of their relevance to human well-being:

[Yes \(go to 13\)](#)

[No, I have other objectives \(go to 2\)](#)

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2

Why are you trying to apply the ecosystem services approach?

To contribute to human well-being through the conservation and sustainable use of natural capital in areas of interest, or as support for land-use planning and territorial management processes, for example.

[Yes \(go to 3\)](#)

[No, I have other objectives \(go to 14\)](#)

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3

The ultimate goal of my project is to improve human well-being through the conservation and sustainable use of natural capital. At this stage, my main focus is to assess the capacity of ecosystems in my study area to produce goods and ecosystem services—in other words, to assess ecosystem service flows.

[Yes \(go to 8\)](#)

[No \(go to 4\)](#)

Beyond the capacity to generate potential benefits, at this stage I am interested in assessing:

- the capture of benefits from ecosystem services;
- their value; and/or
- socio-ecological vulnerability due to the loss of those services.

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At this stage, I am primarily interested in assessing the capture of goods and services from the natural capital of my study area by current beneficiaries.

[Yes \(go to 5\)](#)

[No \(go to 6\)](#)

At this stage I am interested in assessing and mapping:
a) the value of ecosystem services, and/or
b) socio-ecological vulnerability due to the loss of those services.

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To carry out a rapid quantification and mapping of ecosystem service benefits, I am willing to use maps obtained from global models.

[Yes \(go to 17\)](#)

[No \(go to 20\)](#)

I prefer to conduct an ad-hoc quantification and mapping of benefits tailored to my area of interest.

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At this stage, I am primarily interested in assessing the value of the benefits obtained from the capture of ecosystem services (social or economic valuation of ecosystem services).

[Yes \(go to 23\)](#)

[No \(go to 7\)](#)

My main objective is to assess socio-ecological vulnerability due to the loss of ecosystem services.

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At this stage, I am primarily interested in assessing the socio-ecological vulnerability under different scenarios of ecosystem service loss.

Yes (go to 22)

No (go to 14)

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I need a rapid quantification focused on the flow or provision of selected ecosystem services within my area of interest.

Yes (go to 9)

No (go to 10)

I prefer to conduct an ad-hoc quantification and mapping for my area of interest, focused on the flows or production of selected ecosystem functions or services within my system or area of interest.

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To carry out a rapid quantification and mapping of ecosystem service flows, I am willing to use maps obtained from global data or models.

[Yes \(go to 16\)](#)

[No \(go to 15\)](#)

I prefer to transfer estimated or modeled data for land covers and uses similar to those of my area of interest.

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I am interested in obtaining quantitative estimates of biophysical processes (ecosystem functions) in absolute terms (e.g., volume of clean water available per unit of time and space), which allows predictions to be validated. For this, I am willing to apply mechanistic or empirical models of spatially explicit ecosystem processes, which require disciplinary knowledge and involve numerous parameters that must be calibrated.

[Yes \(go to 21\)](#)

[No \(go to 11\)](#)

I prefer to obtain maps of ecosystem service flows through:
a) map modeling or algebra in GIS environments (Geographic Information Systems), or
b) using platforms or applications for standardized assessments.

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I prefer to develop ad-hoc maps of ecosystem service flows using my (or my team's) capacity for spatially explicit modeling through GIS (map algebra).

[Yes \(go to 18\)](#)

[No \(go to 12\)](#)

I prefer to use platforms or applications for standardized assessments.

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I prefer to use platforms or applications for standardized assessments that can run online.

Yes (go to 24)

No (go to 19)

I prefer to use tools that can be installed on my computer (offline) and that do not require an online connection.

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The conservation and management of biodiversity for its intrinsic value or for its use value are not necessarily mutually exclusive objectives. These goals can be complementary and even mutually reinforcing for the same conservation area under both paradigms. However, you should consider that the spatial distribution of priority areas for conservation based on the intrinsic value of biodiversity may be very different from the spatial distribution of priority areas based on the provision of benefits to society. Therefore, and given your primary interest in biodiversity conservation for its intrinsic or conservation value, the ecosystem services approach is not recommended.

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Before continuing with this guide, it seems necessary to further reflect on the objectives that motivate you to explore the application of the ecosystem services approach in your system or area of interest.

Reaching this point implies that you are interested in the sustainable management of ecosystems or some of their components. However, it is possible that your focus is not on the conservation of ecosystems for the intrinsic value of their biodiversity, nor for the value of the benefits derived from it, but rather for the value of certain domesticated, cultivated, or extensively or semi-extensively raised species. In that case, we recommend referring to the knowledge and techniques available for the sustainable management of agricultural and livestock systems (e.g., “good practices manuals”).

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Ecological flow transfer methods

- Jacobs, S., Burkhard, B., Van Daele, T., Staes, J., & Schneiders, A. (2015). The Matrix Reloaded: A review of expert knowledge use for mapping ecosystem services. *Ecological Modelling*, 295, 21–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2014.10.019>

Benefit transfer methods

- Boutwell, J. L., & Westra, J. V. (2013). Benefit transfer: A review of methodologies and challenges. *Resources*, 2(4), 517–527. <https://doi.org/10.3390/resources2040517>
- Plummer, M. L. (2009). Assessing benefit transfer for the valuation of ecosystem services. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 7(1), 38–45. <https://doi.org/10.1890/080091>

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Maps of ecosystem function and service flows available at the global scale

· Chaplin–Kramer, R., Sharp, R. P., Mandle, L., Sim, S., Johnson, J., Butnar, I., ... & Daily, G. C. (2019). Supplementary material. Global modeling of nature's contributions to people. *Science*, 366(6462), 255–258.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaw3372>

· Morales, C., Artés, T., De Biurrun, E., Gregorio, A. D., Fritz, S., & Ceccherini, G. (2023). Earth Map: A novel tool for fast performance of advanced land monitoring and climate assessment. *Journal of Remote Sensing*, 3, 0003.

<https://doi.org/10.34133/remotesensing.0003>

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Maps of benefits available at the global scale

· Chaplin-Kramer, R., Sharp, R. P., Mandle, L., Sim, S., Johnson, J., Butnar, I., ... & Daily, G. C. (2019). Supplementary material. Global modeling of nature's contributions to people. *Science*, 366(6462), 255–258.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaw3372>

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Mapping ecosystem service indicators and indices through spatially explicit modeling using GIS modeling, either offline (ArcGIS – QGIS) or online (Google Earth Engine)

Nahuelhual, L., Laterra, P., & Barrena, J. (2016). Ecosystem services indicators: A review and quality analysis. Ministry of the Environment, Government of Chile. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26830.46403>

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ARIES / INVEST / ECOSER – Flows

· **ARIES:** (ARtificial Intelligence for Environment & Sustainability).

[link](#)

· **InVEST:** (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem, Services and Tradeoffs). [link](#)

· **ECOSER:** Collaborative protocol for the assessment and mapping of ecosystem services and socio-ecological vulnerability for territorial planning. [link](#)

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ECOSER – Benefits

· **ECOSER:** Collaborative protocol for the assessment and mapping of ecosystem services and socio-ecological vulnerability for territorial planning. [link](#)

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Ecosystem process models. Examples:

- **SWAT:** Soil & Water Assessment Tool. [link](#)
- **Waterworld:** [link](#)
- **VFSSMOD:** Vegetative Filter Strip Modeling System.
[link](#)
- **MAIA:** Guidance for the Biophysical Modelling and Analysis of Ecosystem Services in an Ecosystem.
[link](#)

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Socio-ecological vulnerability assessment and mapping

ECOSER: Collaborative protocol for the assessment and mapping of ecosystem services and socio-ecological vulnerability for territorial planning. Module for the assessment and mapping of socio-ecological vulnerability. [link](#)

Useful sources of information for scenario development:

- WRI. Global Forest Watch. (2024). [link](#)
- European Commission. Global Surface Water Explorer. [link](#)
- Pekel, J.-F., Cottam, A., Gorelick, N., Belward, A.S., 2016. High-resolution mapping of global surface water and its long-term changes. Nature 540, 418–422. [link](#)
- PNUMA-CCI. Freshwater Ecosystems Explorer. [link](#)

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InVEST (economic value) – SOLVES (social value)

· **InVEST:** (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem, Services and Tradeoffs). [link](#)

· **SOLVES:** INVEST (Valor económico) – SOLVES (Valor social). [link](#)

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Online tools (viewers and web technologies)

With global coverage:

- Nature Map. [link](#)
- ARIES online. [link](#)
- Co\$ting Nature. [link](#)
- Waterworld. [link](#)

Con cobertura local:

- EnviroAtlas (EPA, USA). Only for North America, but illustrative of integrated environmental viewers. [link](#)
- LIFE Viva Grass (Semi-natural grasslands of Baltic countries). [link](#)

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